

Gender Sensitization - Issues and Challenges of Gender in India

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Abstract

Gender sensitization is a movement through which the people with stereotype and traditional thinking, should be able to assure equal participation of women and men in decision-making and control on the resources to acquire benefits of development and to get equal opportunities in economic, political cultural and social sector. Gender discrimination is a part of gender sensitization. In our society weaker section women are facing many problems. In ancient India, women enjoyed a very high position but gradually their position degenerated into merely objects of pleasure meant to serve certain purpose. They lost their individuality and even their basic human rights. The discrimination is an immoral, unethical and unfairly behavioral practice of an individual and groups of individual who considered himself/herself or themselves differently from the other individuals or groups of individual. As we know that our society is rigid, it is difficult to make changes in the mind set of the people, the government should bring in more welfare schemes for females to make them self-independent. Educational institutions and schools should take initiatives to understand the gender related issues and to sensitize its staff, students and society for the women equality. Government should introduce new programmes and also ensure proper implementation of policies and strategies that ensure gender equality. This paper explains the need of gender sensitization from school level where the process of gender sensitization will bring in social changes relating to women and that gender equality demands empowerment of women with a focus on identifying and redressing power imbalances and giving women more autonomy to manage their own lives. Keeping the status of women empowerment and its determinants in India, an attempt is made to present some of the key determinants of inequality that exists in our country so as to have an idea about to what extent the women are empowered.

Keywords: Gender, Sensitization, Education, Government programmes, Women empowerment

Introduction

Gender inequality in India refers to the health, education, economic and political inequalities between the men and the women in our country. There are various gender inequality indices that rank India differently on each of these factors as well as on composite basis and these indices are controversial. Gender inequalities and their social causes impact India's sex ratio, women's health over their lifetime, their economic condition and their educational achievement. When India's population is examined as a whole, women are at a disadvantage compared to men in several ways. Though our Indian Constitution grants both the men and women equal rights, gender

disparities still continue to remain .Hence gender inequality is a multifaceted issue in India that concerns both men and women.

The gender gap index is a multi dimensional measure of gender inequality .India was scored at 0.66 by the World Economic Forum and was ranked 101 out of 136 countries in the year 2013. Discrimination against women and girls is a long running phenomenon that characterizes Indian society at every level. It is noticed that though Indian GDP has grown by around 6% there is a large decline in the female labour force participation from 34% to 27% .According to a census taken in 2011, India has reached the population of 1210 million of which 48.5 percent were females. Though female literacy has increased from 18.3 percent in 1961 to 74.0 percent, there is still a wide female literacy gap that exists in India.

Objectives

- There is need to sensitize the society on gender issues so that there would be no discrimination on the basis of gender.
- To bring in equal opportunities in education, employment, economic, political, cultural and social sector.
- Introducing various schemes that help girl children and to bring in women empowerment.

Research Methodology

The present study data has been collected from secondary sources. It is collected from magazines, documents of Ministry of Human Resource Development, survey report, Journals and other publications.

Gender Equality and sensitivity

Gender equality can be achieved only when both the men and the women are given equal opportunities, rights and obligations in all spheres of life. Gender equality in other words demands empowerment of women with a focus of identifying and redressing power imbalances and give women more autonomy to manage their lives.

Gender equality is considered a human right which entitles all persons irrespective of their gender. Empowered women make invaluable contribution to the improvement of health condition, productivity of the family and community and also educational status. Gender and its accompanying relatives are built in all institutions of the society be it educational institution, work place, family or even religious systems. Gender gap exists regarding access to education and even employment status. Women exposure to media is less compared to the men in the society. Gender sensitivity is not about pitting women against men but should benefit members of both sexes. The concept of gender equality should be achieved through proper education. There is need to educate the society that will trigger changes but this is possible only when teachers and learners are assisted in adopting classroom initiatives that reflect new images based on a positive gender equality ideology. Various indicators of women empowerment are being analyzed from various sources while discussing women's present status in India. Women's political participation is also analyzed by using indicators like percentage of women voters and women MP.

Review of Literature

Based on a number of studies undertaken on women empowerment at the global level and in India Shields (1995) provided an exploratory framework to know and to develop the concept of empowerment from both theoretical and practical perspective that focus on women's perception of empowerment.

Anand and Sen (1995) tried to develop the concept and measure of gender inequality.

Moser (1993) focused on the development and formulation of gender policy and implementation of gender planning and practices to be followed.

Barkat (2008) discussed the status of women in Bangladesh and learned that though women as mother's are held in high respect on an individual level, there was no awareness about empowerment of women or any participation in decision making or control over her own life.

Chattopadhyay and Duflo (2001) Contributed on women empowerment in the context of India. A policy of political reservation for women in India was used to study the impact of women's leadership on policy decision.

Mahanta (2002) explained the concept of women's access to basic human rights like right to education, health, legal rights, right of working women and also issues on domestic violence.

Development Report (Government of Assam 2003) highlighted the point of inequality in the achievements between men and women of Assam in different spheres of life. This report throws light of the issues concerning poverty, violence and lack of political participation of South Asian women and Assam.

Kishor and Gupta (2004) The author explained that women in India were disempowered compared to men and there has been very little changes happening in her empowerment over time.

Blumerberg (2005) Viewed that the key to gender equality is through economic empowerment of women which is required for the well being of our nation. This would not only enhance the capacity in decision making but will reduce corruption and conflict and violence against women in the long run.

UNDP (1990) for the first time introduced the concept of Human Development Index (HDI) that evolved initially as a broader measure of socio-economic progress of a nation but also became very popular as a measure of average achievement in Human development for both the sexes. Contrary to the general belief that development is gender neutral, statistics show that all over the world, women lag behind men including India in all aspects of life. The report clearly noted that without empowering women overall development of human beings cannot be achieved or made possible. If there exists greater gender disparity in human development, the country's GDI (Gender Development Index) would be lower compared to HDI.

For India to maintain its position as a global growth leader ,more efforts at local and national levels and by the private sector are required to bring women in par with men. There is need for some form of affirmative action to be taken to increase the representation of women in public spheres. There is also a need for change in the attitude of the society for considering women to be equal to men within their homes and in the broader society. There is also a need to educate our children from a very early age about the importance of gender equality.

Literacy Rate in India in 2017-2018

Today the literacy rate in India has been improving .However the female literacy level is less compared to the male literacy rate. The most literate state is Kerala with 93.91 percent, whereas the least literate state in India is Bihar with 63.82 percent.

S. No.	State	Literacy Rate	Male literacy rate	Female literacy rate
1	Assam	73.18	78.81	67.27
2.	Bihar	63.82	73.39	53.33
3.	Delhi	86.34	91.03	80.93
4.	Kerala	93.91	96.02	91.98

5.	Tamil Nadu	80.33	86.81	73.86
6.	West Bengal	77.08	82.67	71.16

Source: www.pinindia.net>literacy-rate

Gender Parity Index (2014-2015)

Level	All	SC	ST
Primary (I-V)	1.03	1.02	0.98
Upper Primary (VI-VIII)	1.09	1.09	1.02
Elementary(I-VIII)	1.05	1.04	0.99
Secondary (IX-X)	1.01	1.03	1.01
Senior Secondary (XI-XII)	0.99	1.03	0.95
Higher Education	0.92	0.91	0.81

Source: Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt of India website

Gender Parity Index is the ratio of the number of female students enrolled at primary, secondary and tertiary level of education to the corresponding number of male students in each level. During the period 2014-15 there is only a very substantial progress being achieved towards gender parity in education as shown in the above table.

Literacy Rates 7+ age group (2001-2011)

	2001			2011		
	ALL	SC	ST	ALL	SC	ST
Total	64.8	54.7	47.1	73.0	66.1	59.0
Male	75.3	67.0	59.0	80.9	75.2	68.5
Female	53.7	42.0	35.0	64.6	56.5	49.4

Adult Literacy 15+ age group

	2001			2011		
	ALL	SC	ST	ALL	SC	ST
Total	61.0	44.1	40.8	69.3	60.4	51.9
Male	73.4	59.3	54.8	78.8	71.6	63.7
Female	47.8	28.5	26.7	59.3	48.6	40.2

Source: Ministry of Human Resource Development, Dept.of school Education and literacy New Delhi 2016

The above tables show that the adult literacy level of the female has increased from 2001 to 2011, but is much lesser than the male. It is also noted that the literacy level of 7+ age category of females are more than the 15+ age category of females. Hence it is clear from the table that very few female go for higher education compared to the male.

Economic Survey 2018 on Female Labour Force Participation

Stressing on the need to increase women participation in labour force, the survey today said that lower women engagement adversely affects the growth potential of the economy, It is noted that women earn very less wages compared to the men in India. The survey observed that women

workers are the most disadvantaged in the labour market as they constitute a very high proportion among the low skilled informal worker category and are involved in low-productivity and low paying work. Owing to this, it is said that women earn low wages and their jobs are highly insecure. India has the largest gender gap in median earnings of full time employees in 2015, in comparison to countries like South Africa, Brazil and Chile. The female workforce registered a decline in the financial year 2015-16 as revealed by Ministry of State for Labour and Employment in a reply to Lok Sabha questions in the winter session of Parliament. In the first four months of 2017 while jobs for men increased by 9 lakh, 24 lakh women fell off the employment map according to (CMIE) Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy.

The survey also stressed for political empowerment of women saying their representation in Parliament and in decision making roles in public sphere is one of the key indicators of empowerment

As per the report women in politics 2017, the Lok Sabha has 64 (11.8% of 542 MP) and the Rajya Sabha had 27(11%)of the 245 MP's), women MP's. As on October 2016, out of the total 4,118 MLA's across the country, only 9 percent were women. Among the state assemblies, the highest percentage of women MLA's were from Bihar, Haryana and Rajasthan-14 percent, Madya Pradesh and West Bengal -13 percent, Punjab -12 percent. (Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation 2016) The survey pointed out that in India between 2010 and 2017 women's representation rose by 1 percent point.

Constraints to Women Empowerment

One of the constraints that check the process of women empowerment in India is the social norms and family structures. The hold of this preference has strengthened rather than weakened and its most glaring evidence is in the falling sex ratio (Seth 2001) The main cause for this type of attitude lies in the old school of thought that male children inherit the clan in India except in Meghalaya. Another main factor that hinders the process of empowerment is the lack of awareness about the constitutional provisions in favour of women.

According to the latest "Monster Salary Index" men earned a median gross hourly salary of Rs.231 compared to women who earned only Rs.184.8. The overall gender pay gap of 20% is a considered a wide gap. As per the report, men with 0-2 years of experience earned 7.8 percent higher median wages than women and those with 6-10 years experience earned 15.3 percent more. This monster salary Index is an initiative by India in collaboration with paycheck. in and IIM – Ahmadabad as a research partner.

Affirmative Action

There is a need for policy initiatives to empower women as gender disparities in India persist even against the backdrop of economic growth. Recent initiatives on training and recruiting women from rural areas to provide factory based jobs in cities give them economic independence and social autonomy that they were unaccustomed to, in their parental homes. Another policy change aimed at, is to equalize in the land inheritance rights between sons and daughters that have been achieved. There is an increase in the educational attainment and also the marriageable age for daughters.

The Indian Government has recognized women's issues and their contribution to the country's economy. Some of the women empowerment initiatives are

- a) Mahila E-Haat: A programme to support women entrepreneurs, Self Help Group and NGO to showcase products made and services rendered by them.
- b) Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao: This is a social campaign aimed at eradication of female foeticide and raising awareness of welfare services for young Indian girls.

- c) Swadhar Greh: The swadhar scheme was launched by the Union Ministry of women and Child Development in 2002 for rehabilitation of women in difficult circumstances. The beneficiaries include widows deserted by their families and relatives.
- d) STEP: The support to training and Employment Programme for women scheme aims to provide skills that give employability to women and to provide competencies and skill that enable women to become self employed or entrepreneurs.
- e) Nari Shakti Puruskar: The Nari Shakti Puruskars are National Level awards recognizing the efforts made by women and institutions in rendering distinguished services for the cause of women.

Summary

Various indicators of women empowerment are analyzed from various sources while discussing the present status of women in India. Women's participation in political field is also being analyzed by using indicators like percentage of women voters and women MP. It is also noticed that acceptance of unequal gender norms by women themselves are still prevailing in our country. There is also a large gender gap that exists in employment, education and also wages distribution. Similarly it is noticed that 50 percent of the women employed are not being paid properly for their work. Looking into all these factors, the women in India are comparatively disempowered and they do not enjoy equal status to the men in our society. Unless the attitude of the people does not change or women themselves changed, women would be denied equal opportunity to that of men.

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